

which gives a relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant. The vibration frequency is dependent on the reduced mass μ of the participating atoms and the restoring forces K between atoms, all other terms remaining constant. When the equilibrium distance between the positive and negative atoms of the molecule is decreased, K generally increases in the above equation. This equilibrium distance depends on the ionic radii of the participating atoms in the molecule. The effect of diminished force constant is reinforced by the increase in mass of the substituted $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ ion which shifts ν_3 and ν_4 of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ bands to lower frequencies. This theoretical explanation agrees well with the experimental data.

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References

1. W. F. VANWAZER in "Phosphorous and its Compounds", Interscience Publishers, London, 1966, Vol. I, p. 530.
2. S. V. CHIRANJEEVIRAO, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1974, **46**, 55.
3. S. V. CHIRANJEEVIRAO, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1975, **47**, 55.
4. K. NAKAMOTO in "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1962, p. 103.
5. R. B. BARNES, R. C. GORE, V. LIDDEL and V. Z. WILLIAMS in "Infrared Spectroscopy", Reinhold, New York, 1944.

Chemistry of Benzoquinolines. Part VI

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IN our previous paper¹ we have reported the reactions of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I) with aromatic aldehydes. The mono styryl derivatives so formed were oxidised to mono-carboxylic acid, which on decarboxylation gave 4-methyl-7,8-benzoquinoline. In the present paper we have studied the reactions of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline(I) further.

Fig. (I) R = CH₃
 (II) R = -CH = CHC₆H₅
 (III) R = *m*-O₂NC₆H₄CH = CH-
 (IV) R = COOH
 (V) R = H

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I) m.p. 54°-55° was prepared in accordance with Combes². 2,4-Distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (II) m.p. 180°-81° was prepared by refluxing 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (1 mole) with excess of benzaldehyde (4 moles) for 32 hr in presence of acetic anhydride. 2,4-Di-(3'-nitro) styryl-7,8-benzoquinoline m.p. 281°-82° was prepared by heating the base (I; 1 mole) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (2 moles) in presence of acetic anhydride at 160° for 4 hr. The above condensation did not take place when fused zinc chloride was used as condensing agent. The procedure followed by Singh and Lal³ also failed to give any fruitful result, though time of refluxing was increased to 96 hr.

The presence of -CH = CH- in distyryls (II) and (III) is confirmed by infrared absorption at 1600 cm⁻¹. latter shows strong bands at 1516 cm⁻¹ and 1341 cm⁻¹, both very strong characteristic for -NO₂ group.

The 2,4-distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline was oxidised with KMnO₄ in acetone³ and 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid (IV) m.p. 262°-63° (decomp.) was obtained. This acid has also been prepared by Silberg⁴ who reported the same melting point for this acid. On decarboxylation of this acid with sodalime 7,8-benzoquinoline⁵ (V) m.p. 51°-52° was obtained, which gave silky picrate m.p. 190°-91°.

In 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid absorption at 3000 cm⁻¹ (broad) shows the presence of hydrogen bonded acid -O-H...O<. A very strong band at 1685 cm⁻¹ is due to C = O of the carboxylic acid. The absence of these bands in compounds (I), (II) and (III) shows the absence of carbonyl group in them.

This dicarboxylic acid is claimed to have been prepared by Schenck and Bailey⁶ by oxidation of base (I) with SeO₂ and they reported its m.p. to be 162°-63°. We also carried out oxidation of base (I) with SeO₂ and obtained an acid which melted at 260°-61°. There was no depression in melting point, when m.p. of this acid was taken in admixture with the acid (IV). Therefore m.p. 162°-63° reported by Schenck and Bailey for this acid does not seem to be correct. We have already reported the m.p. of 4-methyl-7,8-benzoquinoline-2-carboxylic acid to be 186° and it is expected that m.p. of 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid should be higher than that of mono carboxylic acid. Hence m.p. 262°-63° for dicarboxylic acid (IV) is reasonably correct.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected and IR spectra were taken in KBr.

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I)

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline was prepared by following the method of Combes². Recrystallised from ethanol colourless crystals, m.p. 54°-55°. (Found : C, 86.5; H, 6.4. C₁₅H₁₃N requires C, 86.9; H, 6.2%) ν_{max} 1451 (CH₃), 754 (four adjacent H), 802 and 863 (two adjacent H) and 887 cm⁻¹ (one isolated H).

2,4-Distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (II)

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (15.1 g) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (36 g) were refluxed for 32 hr in presence of acetic anhydride. The excess of benzaldehyde was removed by steam distillation. The liquid was poured in 100 ml of 20% NaOH solution. Yellow mass separated. Recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and ether petrol (60°–80°). Yellow crystals (19 g), m.p. 180°–81°. It gives bluish fluorescence with benzene, acetone, ethanol and ether. (Found: C, 90.1; H, 6.0. $C_{29}H_{21}N$ requires C, 9.08; H, 5.48%), ν_{max} 1600 and 1577 (–CH = CH–) 733 (four adjacent H), 850 (two adjacent H), 8,80–894 cm^{-1} (one isolated H).

2,4-Di-(3'-nitro)styryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (III)

A mixture of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (20.7 g), *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (30.2 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was heated at 160° for 4 hr. The mixture was poured in 200 ml of 20% NaOH solution. The yellow mass separated. Recrystallised from xylene. Yellow crystals m.p. 281°–82°. It was insoluble in benzene, chloroform and ethanol. (Found: C, 73.4; H, 4.2. $C_{29}H_{19}N_3O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.1%), ν_{max} 1600 and 1576 (–CH = CH–), 724 (four adjacent H), 820 (three adjacent H), 870 (one isolated H), 1516 and 1341 cm^{-1} (–NO₂).

7,8-Benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid (IV)

This was prepared following the procedure of Singh and Lal³. Recrystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ether petrol (60°–80°). Yellow crystals, m.p. 262°–63° (decomp.). It is insoluble in ether, benzene, acetone but soluble in alcohol. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 3.0. $C_{15}H_9NO_4$ requires C, 67.4; H, 3.3%), ν_{max} 1685 (C = O), 3000 (OH, hydrogen bonded), 740 (four adjacent H), 830 (two adjacent H) and 880 cm^{-1} (one isolated H).

7,8-Benzoquinoline (V)

A mixture of 2,4-dicarboxyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (0.4 g) and sodalime (0.5 g) was heated strongly. A few drops of yellow liquid deposited which solidified as yellowish brown crystals, m.p. 51°–52°, picrate m.p. 190°–91°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.0. $C_{13}H_9N$ requires C, 87.1; H, 5.02%).

Oxidation of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline with SeO₂

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I, 1.2 g) and SeO₂ (2 g) were refluxed for 16 hr in ethanol (20 ml). The solution was evaporated to dryness and residue was taken up in acetone. 30% H₂O₂ (5 ml) was added and mixture refluxed for 1 hr. Acetone was removed and solid residue was extracted with ethanol and solution was concentrated. Yellow crystals were obtained. Recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 260°–61° with blackening at 258°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 3.5. $C_{15}H_9NO_4$ requires C, 67.4; H, 3.3%), ν_{max} 1685 (C = O), 3000 (broad, H bonding), 740 (four adjacent H), 830 (two adjacent H), 880 (one isolated H).

References

1. P. N. SINGH and N. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 1016.
2. COMBES, *Compt. Rend.*, 1888, 106, 1536.
3. N. SINGH and A. B. LAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 352.
4. AL SILBERG, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1939, 6, 510.
5. *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 9214.
6. SCHENCK and BAILEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2331.

A New Method Depending on the Use of the Rotating Pt-Electrode at Zero applied e.m.f. for Micro-determination of Nitrite

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CHOW and Robinson¹ determined nitrite polarographically in presence of MoO₄²⁻ as catalyst. Several oxidants were previously described for the determination of nitrite depending upon its oxidation to nitrate²⁻⁷. Recently, Issa *et al.*⁸ determined nitrite by back titration with KMnO₄ in fluoride medium and the lower limit of nitrite determined was 0.093 mg.

In the present investigation, we describe a new method for microdetermination of nitrite. It depends upon amperometric titration with potassium permanganate in acid medium containing fluoride ions using the rotating Pt-electrode vs S.O.E. as reference at zero applied e.m.f. The factors affecting the success of the method are studied.

Experimental

Reagents

Preparation of solutions: Potassium permanganate solutions were prepared by a method similar to that of Stamm⁹ and standardized with sodium oxalate¹⁰ (normality of permanganate solutions used is based on valency change of Mn⁺⁷ to Mn⁺³). Sodium nitrite solutions were prepared by dissolving the A.R. product in double distilled water and standardized according to recommended procedure⁴. Solutions of permanganate and nitrite of required concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution. Other solutions including 2% sodium fluoride, 1*N* sulfuric acid and 0.5*N* copper sulfate were prepared from the A.R. chemicals.

Titration procedure

The amperometric titration assembly used consisted of a beaker, rotating Pt-electrode, agar bridge, saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) and microburette. The attainment of a steady diffusion current was maintained by rotating the Pt-electrode at a constant speed of 600 r.p.m. The nitrite solution was mixed with the appropriate amount of sulfuric acid and/or with sulfuric acid, sodium fluoride and copper sulfate,